

VIROPLANT

D5.7 – REPORT ON RISK ASSESSMENT

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1. INTRODUCTION

VIROPLANT introduces the possibility of using new classes of viruses and the virus-induced gene silencing (VIGS) approach to limit the effect of bacterial and fungal/oomycetes plant diseases and limit the direct and indirect damage caused by insect pest and vectors.

Although the concept of using viruses for biocontrol is not new, and some commercial products are registered in Europe and elsewhere, the risk associated to their use has been thoroughly evaluated only in the case of Baculoviruses, the only registered virus-based plant protection product (PPP) in Europe together with a mild strain of pepino mosaic virus to be used in cross protection (Efsa, 2017) (not relevant for the VIROPLANT project, which does not include cross protection products).

Here we aim at presenting a theoretical risk assessment regarding phage biocontrol for plant bacterial diseases, the use of Gemycirculavirus for the containment of fungal diseases, the use of densovirus/iflavivirus for insect pest and vectors, and finally the use of VIGS that targets phytopathogenic fungi and insect pest and vectors.

A previous EU funded project (REBECA) (Ehlers, 2011) has resulted in a thorough assessment of the regulation of biological control agents, with specific model cases of risk assessment, arguing for some simplification of the regulatory burden when feasible. In that project the only viruses under consideration were baculoviruses (Hauschild, 2011); here we will introduce an initial evaluation, purely theoretical, based on literature (very limited yet), and some interviews with scientists.

EFSA also issued two external scientific reports which provide one of the most comprehensive literature reviews of biopesticide hazard/risk assessment (Hackl et al., 2015; Mudgal et al., 2013), which will be used to guide the risk assessment for each of the chosen case-studies.

Specifically, regarding the risk assessment for **human health**, the following topics will be covered:

- 1) Evaluation of Pathogenicity, Infectivity and Toxicity
- 2) Transfer of genetic material and insertional mutagenesis

Related to the **environmental risk assessment**, we will cover the following topics:

- 1) Genetic Stability and Transfer
- 2) Interference with the system for drinking water quality control
- 3) Fate and behavior in the environment
- 4) Ability to produce toxic metabolites with potential effects on non-target organisms
- 5) Host specificity and potential effect on non-target organisms:
 - a) Bees and pollinators
 - b) Useful insects
 - c) Birds, mammals, plants

2. CASE STUDY 1: A PHAGE-BASED PRODUCT TO LIMIT A PLANT PATHOGENIC BACTERIAL DISEASE

Phage biocontrol in agriculture is a developing field, that is beginning to result in commercial formulations: in the USA, at least four distinct commercial formulations are available, and they received a fast-track registration process with the US EPA (<https://www.omnilytics.com/agriculture/>). The four products are against *Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *syringae* and *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *vesicatoria* (bacterial speck and spot in tomato and pepper), *Clavibacter michiganensis* subsp. *michiganensis* (bacterial canker in tomato), *Erwinia amylovora* (fireblight in pears and apples) and *Xanthomonas citri* subsp. *citri* (bacterial canker in citrus). In 2021, US EPA has allowed the registration of a new phage cocktail by A&P Inphatec against Pierce's disease of grapevine, a disease caused by *Xylella fastidiosa*, with limited control options but with a huge economic impact (<https://agrifliferoday.tamu.edu/2021/05/28/texas-am-agrilife-research-develops-bacteriophage-treatment-for-pierces-disease/>).

In Europe, so far, the only phage-based products registered for agricultural purposes (but not as pesticides) are those of APS Biocontrol linked to post-harvest treatments of soft rot of potato, which is caused by *Pectobacterium* spp. (<https://www.apsbiocontrol.com/products>). Recent registration in the USA of phage products for treating food in controlled environments have granted them "GRAS" status (Generally Regarded As Safe). In this regard, EFSA excluded bacteriophages from the qualified presumption of safety list (QPS) list (Hazards et al., 2020).

Regarding a risk assessment specific for phage biocontrol in agriculture, not much is available based on experimental approaches. Inside VIROPLANT, a specific task addressing environmental risk assessment in a phage biocontrol model is going to be presented in a deliverable due at month 42 (D2.8). Here, we will instead look at the general outline of the different hazards associated to the implementation of phages against plant diseases.

We will use as background information a paper that looked at the contained use of bacteriophages (Verheust et al., 2010), trying to incorporate specificities due to the fact that treatment of bacterial plant disease requires dispersal in the environment. A recent review also summarizes the main registration hurdles present in Europe compared to USA (Stefani et al., 2021).

We will first look at some hypothetical hazards for humans and the environment.

2.1 PATHOGENICITY FOR HUMANS

2.1.1 DIRECT PATHOGENICITY

Phages are generally thought to be harmless to humans, but there are some examples where bacteria become pathogenic because of the presence of a prophage sequence in their genomes that encodes for a specific toxin: some relevant examples of this so-called "phage lysogenic conversion" are those involved in cholera (Cholera

toxin encoded by the phage CTXphi in *Vibrio cholerae*), scarlet fever (SpeC toxin encoded by phiCS112 phage in *Streptococcus pyogenes*) and botulism (Botulinum toxin encoded by clostridial phages in *Clostridium botulinum*) (Broudy and Fischetti, 2003; Sakaguchi et al., 2005; Waldor and Mekalanos, 1996). Phages not only can encode for toxins, but also for virulence factors. Sequence analysis and proper annotation of the entire phage genome is therefore a requirement to look for evidences of presence of homologues to toxins or to virulence factors.

2.1.2 INDIRECT PATHOGENICITY THROUGH EFFECTS ON THE HUMAN MICROBIOTA

A wealth of recent work has pointed to the many beneficial effects of the human-associated microbiota on many aspects of physical and mental health (Alam et al., 2017; Michail et al., 2012; Scher and Abramson, 2011; Ubeda and Pamer, 2012), not only in the gut, but also in other niches such as the eye (Shin et al., 2016), nasal (Heintz-Buschart et al., 2018), oral and genital (Ma et al., 2012) cavities. Therefore, a proper theoretical risk assessment for the effects of phage therapy on humans should also take into account the possibility of alterations of the microbiota, which is normally done by antibiotics (Ganeshan and Hosseinidoust, 2019).

In fact, such studies are becoming the focus of new attention since the first successful proof of concept cure of a dysbiotic liver disorder associated to phage therapy (Duan et al., 2019). Given that these treatments address a single component of a complex network of interdependent organisms, it is important to look at direct and indirect effects on the communities that characterize a specific microbiome. For example in a specific cornerstone study published in 2019, Hsu and colleagues showed in a simplified gnotobiotic mouse model, in which 10 human gut bacteria were implanted, that complex interrelationships among the species were present and that targeting one single species could cause bloom and burst of other species; also very importantly, they showed that in principle this had an effect on the metabolome characterizing the bacterial community (Hsu et al., 2019).

Another indirect effect is the possibility that phage therapy against a specific host might result in a host jump to a resistant species present in the community (De Sordi et al., 2017). These host jumps happen only in the gut but not *in vitro*, and probably require intermediate hosts from the microbiota: such adaptation requires intragenomic recombination events.

In another study, the overall the effect on the complexity of the microbiota seem to be minimal (Galtier et al., 2016).

Nevertheless, given the specificity of phage-host relationship and the very limited or non-existing taxonomical representation of phylogenetically related bacteria between the human microbiota at large and plant pathogens, it is unlikely that phage biocontrol for plant bacterial diseases can have any off-target effect on the human microbiota: a taxonomic/phylogenetic comparison between plant pathogenic bacteria and human gut microbiota-characterizing taxa could indicate the likeliness of possible off-target effects.

2.2 ENVIRONMENTAL RISK ASSESSMENT FOR PHAGE THERAPY

As mentioned above, environmental risk assessment of phage biocontrol against plant pathogens is widely discussed in Deliverable 2.8. Here below, we only discuss a specific point on gene transfer capacity.

2.2.1 GENE TRANSFER CAPACITY

Phages play a key role in bacterial evolution, and one of the most important mechanisms behind it is transduction, which is a mechanism that uses phage capsids to encapsidate fragments of a bacterial genome, thereby transferring them to new bacterial cells. There are two main mechanisms: generalized (a random selection of degraded bacterial DNA is present in the virion) or specialized (when only segments that are close to the prophage sequences are encapsidated due to imprecise excision). Transduction mostly occurs within the same species (determined by the virus host range) but in rare cases, it can involve also different bacterial species. Such mechanism of transfer of genetic material is not an hazard a priori, but only if specific hazardous genes are transferred: some examples are dissemination of antibiotic resistance (Brabban et al., 2005; Schaefer, 1982) or pathogenicity islands (PAIs) (Ruzin et al., 2001). In general, the potential for transduction can be increased if prophages are present in the system, and therefore temperate phages are not considered to be suitable for biocontrol (Roach et al., 2015; Svircev et al., 2018), although this view has recently been challenged (Monteiro et al., 2019).

Another more recently discovered mechanism of increased transduction capability comes from the description of acquired sensitivity (ASEN), where lytic phages can render some resistant cells susceptible through acquisition of receptors from sensitive lysed populations (through vesicles) (Tzipilevich et al., 2017); overall, this mechanism could increase the risk of unintended effects of phage biocontrol on other off-target bacterial species: to what extent this occurs in natural bacterial communities remains to be elucidated.

To prevent such risk, analysis of the host range and the transduction capacity should be investigated.

3. CASE STUDY 2: NATURAL INSECT VIRUSES

We will look here mostly at the evaluation of risk associated to the use of densoviruses, and to a lesser extent of iflaviruses, since a comprehensive risk assessment for baculoviruses has already been carried out, and a number of products are registered in Europe. We will assess risk based on literature and interviews, in specific using as benchmark, the risk posed by baculoviruses, since they are generally considered safe for biocontrol.

3.1 DENSOVIRUS

3.1.1 GENERAL FEATURES

Densovirus belong to the family *Parvoviridae*, subfamily Densovirinae: the other subfamily, Parvovirinae, mostly includes viruses infecting vertebrates. They have a simple genomic organization, with ssDNA genomes ranging in size between 5 and 10 kb protected by an isodiametric coat (Fig. 1).

FIGURE 1: Structural features of densoviruses

They encode for two proteins, the non structural protein (rep), required for their replication, and the coat protein (cap) (Tijssen et al., 2016) (Fig. 2). The REP protein is fairly conserved and used to infer phylogenetic relationships among ssDNA encoded viruses: it is a hallmark of rolling circle replication, which indeed occurs also for densoviruses. They can replicate only hijacking the host DNA polymerase to synthesize ds RNA from ssDNA as a first step of their infectious cycle: such DNA polymerase is available only during the S phase of the cell cycle, and therefore this viruses have a tropism for actively replicating cells.

FIGURE 2: Genomome organization and Expression strategy of Densoviruses.

Their names derive from their hypertrophied nuclei, intensely stained with Feulgen reagent and, when observed at the EM, infected cells display virogenic stroma containing virions and paracrystalline virion arrays.

We have a limited knowledge of the confirmed host range of densoviruses: so far, they have been reported in insects (Lepidoptera, Diptera, Hymenoptera, Blattoidea, Emittera Orthoptera), crustaceans, echinoderms (starfish and sea urchins).

Densoviruses were initially characterized to have strong symptoms, including lethal effects, but more recent untargeted approaches have shown that a number of densoviruses are neutral, or even have a symbiotic effect with their insect hosts. When they display strong symptoms, they start with anorexia and lethargy, progressing to paralysis and melanization. (Bergoin and Tijssen, 2010; Tijssen et al., 2016).

Infections are generally highly contagious and they can be detrimental when they target useful insects, like *Bombix mori* in sericultural farms (Watnabe and Shimizu, 1980), cricket farms (Szelei et al., 2011) and industrial shrimp farming (Lightner, 1996). They are also the cause of a severe sea-star wasting disease (Hewson et al., 2014).

Their pathogenicity can be used for Biocontrol purposes as in the case of Limacodidae larvae in oil palm plantations (Federe et al., 1990) or for mosquitos (Buchatskii et al., 1987; Buchatsky et al., 1987). A Densovirus-based product is used in China against a cockroach species (Jiang et al., 2008).

3.1.2 THE RISK ASSESSMENT FOR HUMAN HEALTH

I) EVALUATION OF INFECTIVITY, EVALUATION OF PATHOGENICITY, EVALUATION OF TOXICITY

One of the main impediment to adopting densoviruses for biocontrol is an old work that reported that they can infect and transform mouse cells L (Kurstak et al., 1969a; Kurstak et al., 1969b). Their findings were based on immunofluorescence, which is not in itself a proof of replication, since immunofluorescence could result simply from uptake. In 2004, El-Far and co-author had the possibility to test with more suitable molecular techniques, the hypothesis of replication of densovirus in vertebrate cells. They indeed had the possibility to compare an insect cell line, readily infected with virus and in vitro synthesized DNA from the virus *Mythimna loreyi* densovirus (MIDNV), a virus that had potential for biocontrol since it can infect a few important lepidopteran pest species (El-Far et al., 2004). Multiple approaches, with proper controls, have shown that indeed vertebrate cells can uptake virus (particularly in the high concentration conditions of the experiment), but the virus can not replicate, or cause cytopathotoxic effects: in specific, the virus could not be transcribed or replicated, and there was no viral integration and no particle production; also the nicking performed by the NS1 protein, a step crucial for genome replication, only occurs in permissive cells (El-Far et al., 2004).

A further element that could help assessing the risk that densoviruses pose to human, is what are the closest human pathogens phylogenetically. Up to a few years ago, it seemed that only members of the parvovirinae, the other subfamily in the *Parvoviridae*, could infect vertebrates. Recently some researchers claim that a virus distantly related to densoviruses, can indeed infect humans: in specific a densovirus was isolated from cerebrospinal fluid of a human case of encephalitis (Tung Gia et al., 2018; Tung Gia et al., 2016; Tung Gia et al., 2015): this specific densovirus is only very distantly related to insect-infecting densoviruses: the authors could

not exclude that the virus was the result of external contamination, and that it had no causative effect with the encephalitis symptoms.

A very recent work also has associated the presence of a densovirus to the plasma virome of 781 Brazilian chosen for Dengue like symptoms, but Dengue virus negative (Fahsbender et al., 2020); again the authors have no evidence of replication and can not exclude the presence of another human parasite as primary host.

Risk of toxicity to humans of insect viruses was also recently evaluated by EFSA in a work related to the risk associated to production and consumption of insects as food and feed (Comm, 2015): the authors consider densovirus, since they very commonly infect crickets, but they use the same arguments we displayed above to exclude the possibility they can harm humans.

II) TRANSFER OF GENETIC MATERIAL AND INSERTIONAL MUTAGENESIS

Densoviruses are ssDNA viruses that enter the nucleus for their replication and use host polymerases for transcription and replication. Their nuclear localization could raise risk alert for their possible integration in human hosts. From this point of view, although there is plenty of evidence that integration can occur in invertebrate hosts, at least in evolutionary time, liket endogenized viral elements in their genomes, there is no evidence that this has ever occurred in genomes of vertebrates (Belyi et al., 2010; Kapoor et al., 2010; Liu et al., 2011). This ample solid literature concurs to a very low risk for insertional mutagenesis in humans since replication is a prerequisite for such occurrence.

Transfer of genetic material to humans is also unlikely, particularly because of the small viral genome that does not allow mechanisms similar to transductions occurring with bacteria, and again, because replication seem to be a requirement for any genetic transfer.

3.1.3 ENVIRONMENTAL RISK ASSESSMENT:

I) GENETIC STABILITY AND TRANSFER

Generally DNA viruses have stable genomes, since they use an error proof set of DNA polymerases: in this respect, ssDNA viruses might be different, since their mutation rate seem to be intermediate with that of RNA viruses that do not have error proof polymerases (Shackelton et al., 2005). Also recombination, although frequent among viruses, does not seem to involve recombination with host genes (Martin et al., 2011). Finally looking more in general at the possibility that viruses are motors of horizontal gene transfer, not only of transposons but also of other genes, it is worth reminding that although traces of single steps of such occurrence (host to virus and virus to host) have been proven experimentally (Gilbert and Cordaux, 2017; Gilbert and Feschotte, 2018), the occurrence of the whole process can only be shown indirectly through analysis of endogenized virus elements: in this respect, densoviruses are particularly prone to be inserted in EVE (Francois et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2011), but only inside hosts where they replicate: therefore host range seems to be still a firewall to HGT among species due to densoviruses.

II) INTERFERENCE WITH THE SYSTEM FOR DRINKING WATER QUALITY CONTROL

There are no specific issues related to interference with quality control of waters, which when involving viruses, has to occur through specific molecular detection methods.

III) FATE AND BEHAVIOR IN THE ENVIRONMENT

Fate and behaviour in the environment strongly depend on application type and pattern: application rate, the frequency, the site (crop, bare soil etc), the time (early or late in the crop, or in the day), type of application (spray, drip, aircraft, ground etc). Since we still have not envisioned a specific application protocol for the possible densovirus-based BCA, we here can only speculate by comparison with baculoviruses properties, and extrapolating some considerations from some field experiments of biocontrol with densoviruses.

As a general feature, densovirus particles are not included in protective occlusions as baculoviruses, which makes them immediately infectious, and at the same time also much more prone to inactivation from environmental factors.

VIRODEN is a densovirus-based BCA that was experimented in Ukraine: it consists of *Aedes aegypti* infected by AeDNV, ground larvae in phosphate-buffered saline and glycerol. Field trials (water reservoirs) in three distinct climatic regions (Ukraine, Russia, Tadjikistan) looked at efficacy, off target effects and persistence in the environment. No off target effect on crustaceans, water beetles and frogs were observed. Bioassays conducted on water samples from treated reservoirs showed that the virus was still present and active after one year from the initial treatment: the authors speculate that this occurs through passing of the virus onto subsequent generations.

IV) ABILITY TO PRODUCE TOXIC METABOLITES WITH POTENTIAL EFFECTS ON NON-TARGET ORGANISMS

Given the small genome, that only encodes two proteins, we can predict the potential for toxicity of those two encoded proteins. In specific when taking into account the risk for the production and consumption of insects as food and feed, virus infection by densoviruses were not considered a risk (Comm, 2015). Therefore, direct or indirect toxicity of virus coded proteins seem to pose a low risk for the use of densovirus as biocontrol agents.

V) HOST SPECIFICITY AND POTENTIAL EFFECT ON NON-TARGET ORGANISMS:

Densoviruses so far described and characterized all belong to insects and to lesser extent to echinoderms and crayfish (Hewson et al., 2014; Tijssen et al., 2016). Nevertheless their host range in the invertebrate is likely larger as inferred thorough endogenized fragments (Francois et al., 2016).

Looking at specific densoviruses, some species have a very limited host range as is the case of *Galleria melonella* densovirus which can only infect *G. melonella*. Some can extend the host range to closely related species, as is the case of *Acheta domestica* densovirus, and finally, *Mythimna loreyi* densovirus can have quite a large insect host range (Tijssen et al., 2016).

Therefore, potential densovirus-based biocontrol agents should indeed experimentally be tested for their ability to infect:

a) Bees and pollinators: densovirus can infect Imenoptera, even if no specific bee or pollinator densovirus was characterized.

b) Useful insects: densovirus can potentially infect many other useful insects, including predators and parasitoids, therefore some specific evaluation of host range could help in determining specific risks. In baculovirus the only effect was due to the direct effect on the target caterpillar, which would have as secondary effect a decreased population of other insect that are predators or parasitoids of the caterpillar itself: such a phenomenon can be predicted for densovirus-based BCA, without having a specific hazard.

c) Birds, mammals, plants

Recently a densovirus was characterized from great tit (*Parus major*) (Yang et al., 2016): in specific the virus was found in lung tissue; the specific virus found in great tit, is closely related (but distinct from) *Blattella germanica* densovirus; the virus is cytopathic to feline kidney cells; the authors state that no proof that this virus can infect bird is actually given, and further work would be necessary. As for densovirus infecting mammals, so far, neither EVE studies, nor NGS study of have shown evidence that insect densovirus can infect mammals; nevertheless, a plethora of densoviruses can be found in vertebrate's feces, since most of them will indeed eat insects.

Insect viruses in general can not infect plants, although in a specific experiment an RNA insect virus belonging to the nodaviridae (Flock house virus=FHV) was shown to replicate in barley protoplast and accumulate locally in other plant hosts (Selling et al., 1990); later it was shown that systemic infection could be obtained if a plant virus movement protein is provided in trans (Dasgupta et al., 2001); this are highly artificial settings that have not evidence of occurring in natural conditions. To the best of our literature search, densoviruses can not infect plants.

3.2 IFLAVIRUS

3.2.1 GENERAL FEATURES

Iflaviruses belong to the family *Iflaviridae*, in the order *Picornavirales*. They form icosahedral particles of 30 nm in diameter and contain a ssRNA genome of circa 10kb length of positive polarity. Their expression strategy comprises the expression of a polyprotein that is proteolytically processed and starts after a long UTR with an IRES site (van Oers, 2010) (Figure 3)..

FIGURE 3. Structural features and expression strategies of I flaviruses.

They only infect arthropods: mostly insects (Lepidoptera, Hymenoptera and Emittera) and a bee parasitic mite (order Acarina) (Valles et al., 2017).

As with most viruses, this group of virus was characterized because of the detrimental effect it caused to insects that are used by humans: the first proven virus of insect (filterable infectious disease) was indeed the Sacbrood bee virus discovered at the beginning of the previous century (White, 1913). It causes a severe pathology in bee colonies, consisting of the impossibility to shed the last larval skin.

The second example is the causal agent of an infectious diarrhea of the silkworm *B. mori*, named infectious flacherie virus, which became the type member of this family (Aizawa and Kurata, 1964).

Since NGS approaches have been used, more and more iflavirus-like sequences have been associated to insects, and it seems that covert symptomless infections are common in this family (Abba et al., 2017; Jakubowska et al., 2016).

3.2.2 THE RISK ASSESSMENT FOR HUMAN HEALTH

I) EVALUATION OF INFECTIVITY, EVALUATION OF PATHOGENICITY, EVALUATION OF TOXICITY

There are no specific studies evaluating the risk for human infection, but the family *I flaviridae* only contains viruses that can infect invertebrates, and therefore the risk seems to be minimal. Attempts at infecting vertebrate cell lines, should be included in a safety assessment.

II) TRANSFER OF GENETIC MATERIAL AND INSERTIONAL MUTAGENESIS

Compared to the densoviruses, I flaviruses seem to pose a lower risk for a number of reasons: i) they are RNA viruses that do not replicate in the nucleus; ii) there is no evidence of widespread endogenous viral elements

in genome of Iflavirus genomes not even in invertebrate hosts; iii) they are a taxonomic group that only infects invertebrates (mostly insects).

3.2.3 ENVIRONMENTAL RISK ASSESSMENT:

I) GENETIC STABILITY AND TRANSFER

Compared to DNA viruses (Baculovirus and Densovirus) mutation rate of RNA polymerases of Iflaviruses is that typical of error prone viral RNA polymerases: nevertheless, this high point mutation rate, which is essential for the adaptive potential of iflaviruses, does not seem to allow unpredicted host jumps, since iflaviruses only were found in insects. Recombination occurs but again without challenging the general stability of the virus in the times foreseen for biocontrol intervention. RNA viruses in general can often encapsidate host RNA (contrary to DNA viruses) and this can be transferred to recipient hosts (as are the well-studied cases of the nodavirus flock house virus and cucumber necrosis virus) but without contributing to genetic alteration in the host (Ghoshal et al., 2015; Rochon et al., 1991).

II) INTERFERENCE WITH THE SYSTEM FOR DRINKING WATER QUALITY CONTROL

As for densoviruses, there are no specific issues related to interference with quality control of waters, which when involving viruses, has to occur through specific molecular detection methods.

III) FATE AND BEHAVIOR IN THE ENVIRONMENT

Very little is known about studies addressing this aspect, but in general infectivity of the virus reduces quickly (Hitchcock, 1966)

IV) ABILITY TO PRODUCE TOXIC METABOLITES WITH POTENTIAL EFFECTS ON NON-TARGET ORGANISMS

As stated for Densovirus, the very limited genome size, and the compact expression strategy that results only in 7-10 well characterized proteins, seem to exclude also in this case the potential for direct toxicity due to virus particle composition or virus-infected cells. Infection with iflavirus (common in some edible insects) did not raise any specific concern in previous risk assessment performed for production and consumption of insects as food and feed (Comm, 2015). In general, there are no reasons to think that iflavirus are more hazardous in this respect than baculoviruses.

V) HOST SPECIFICITY AND POTENTIAL EFFECT ON NON-TARGET ORGANISMS:

a) Bees and pollinators: hymenopteran insects, and bees in particular are infected commonly by Iflaviruses, therefore a specific assay for infectivity in these hosts should be part of a proper risk assessment

b) Useful insects: given that dipteran and hymenopteran are among the insects used to control other insects, and that they can be infected by iflaviruses, the potential for off target infection is also present; a specific assays should be carried out if an iflavirus-based product is to be registered

c) Birds, mammals, plants: in this case, iflaviruses do not seem to be a realistic threat, given that iflaviruses do not infect vertebrates or plants (van Oers, 2010).

4. CASE STUDY 3: THE CHALLENGING RISK ASSESSMENT OF NEW BIOCONTROL APPROACHES BASED ON MYCOVIRUSES.

Mycoviruses have been at the center of attention since the late seventies when it was demonstrated that hypovirulence in *Cryphonectria parasitica*, the causal agent of chestnut blight was caused by the presence of a mycovirus, *Cryphonectria hypovirus 1* (CHV1), a member of the family *Hypoviridae* (Choi and Nuss, 1992; Vanalfen et al., 1975). Since then, other fungal pathogens were investigated for the presence of mycoviruses to be exploited as biocontrol agents. Such surveys did not result in any new real agent of field deployable hypovirulence until the recent discovery of ssDNA mycoviruses (Yu et al., 2010), mycoviruses which have a completely different life cycle and relationship with the fungal hosts, which has stimulated new interested in mycoviruses as plant protection products. Here below we will briefly address the research advances in the development of mycovirus-based biocontrol agents and address some theoretical aspects of the different risks and hazards linked to new approaches.

4.1 USE OF MYCOVIRUSES FOR BIOCONTROL OF FUNGI: THE TRADITIONAL HYPOVIRULENCE APPROACH VS NEW APPROACHES

4.1.1: EPIDEMIOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF OLD AND NEW MYCOVIRUSES: MYCOVIRUS TRANSMISSION MODALITIES

A dogma related to mycoviruses that was only recently broken (with the discovery of a new class of mycoviruses with new properties) is the fact that mycovirus do not have an extracellular stage in their life cycle: in other words, mycoviruses never exists outside cells as infectious particles, and can be transmitted among different fungal individual through anastomosis (Nuss, 2005). Anastomosis is a hyphal fusion phenomenon among individuals of the same fungal species that is tightly regulated by a number of different alleles at different loci: the model fungus for the genetic control of such regulation is indeed *C. parasitica*, because anastomosis and its regulation by somatic incompatibility genes are a key regulatory checkpoint for virus transmission among fungal individuals (Choi et al., 2012; Dawe and Nuss, 2013). Lack of cell fusions among different species controlled by intersterility genes is one of the main reasons for the natural confinement of mycovirus to a specific host, even though exception to a very strict host-specificity are known.

Such dogma has been questioned with a few not fully convincing exceptions in traditional dsRNA mycoviruses, but was finally broken after the discovery of the first ssDNA mycovirus named *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum* ssDNA hypovirulence associated virus (Yu et al., 2010). In later studies the authors convincingly

demonstrated that this virus can be uptaken directly as virus particle from the environment by the fungus during growth (Yu et al., 2013). Furthermore, the role of a possible insect vector was also shown, with further implication for risk assessment (Liu et al., 2016).

4.1.2: DIFFERENT APPROACHES FOR MYCOVIRUS-BASED BIOCONTROL

The modality of transmission of a mycovirus among individuals in a population of potential hosts has different implications for the specific therapeutic approach to fight a fungal-caused plant disease.

The traditional approach relies on anastomosis (hyphal fusion) between individuals of the same species: in this approach the mycovirus-containing hypovirulent strain is introduced to treat single *C. parasitica* caused cankers and then through conversion of the virulent strains when the latter also gets infected by the mycovirus: in this way, the hypovirulent strain is introduced in the forest/orchard and remains indefinitely in the environment to operate continuously conversion of virulent strains and somewhat reducing the overall effect of the disease in chestnut orchards. In this respect, the burden of introducing the hypovirulent strain has been on public bodies, and no real commercial registration of hypovirulent strains was pursued. In this case, the virus is never really freely released in the environment, and in this respect, it could be argued that is simply a maternal genetic element of the hypovirulent strain.

Such an approach has many limitations, particularly on annual crops. Furthermore, vegetative compatibility barriers limit the possibility of a general transmission of the virus to all the necessary recipient strains. For this reason, usually the virus is transmitted to a local *C. parasitica* strain to allow efficient spread, which is a labour-intensive step and does not allow the registration of a single biocontrol product. Also, *C. parasitica* is in a way ideal because in Europe it has very low population variation compared to native pathogens that may have a very large population size and if virus transmission is controlled by vegetative incompatibility, the virus transmission would be very limited.

In this respect the discovery of ssDNA mycoviruses and their specific biological features allows for the first time to envision a second mycovirus-based biocontrol approach: in this case, virus particles are indeed infectious and are absorbed from the environment through an unknown mechanism and can initiate hyphal fungal infection affecting the virulence of the host, *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum*. In this case we can use mycovirus particles as a mycocidal product, without relying on anastomosis from a carrier strain (Yu et al., 2013).

A more recent mycovirus-based biocontrol approach relies on the discovery of the complex relationship of a mycovirus-infected hypovirulent strain with the plants that need protection. Basically, in this case it was shown that the mycovirus can switch the fungal host from pathogen to endophyte (mode?), and that the presence of the endophytic fungus in the plant hosts has positive effects on the growth of the plant and on the protection from the virus-free pathogen (Zhang et al., 2020; Zhou et al., 2021). Surprisingly such endophytic relationship can be established also with a gramineous host and it can prime the plant to protect itself from a number of different fungal pathogens not related with the species of the mycovirus-infected endophytic stage (Binnian Tian, 2020). In this third approach, the product that is sprayed on the crop is indeed a fungal culture that carries the mycovirus intracellularly, therefore there is no open release of the virus in the environment;

nevertheless, it acts as a biocontrol agent without the necessity to convert the recipient strain through anastomosis.

4.2 THEORETICAL RISK ASSESSMENT OF THE MYCOCIDAL APPROACH

As mentioned above, the option of using mycovirus as fungicides, directly through formulations on the plants is generally restricted by their life style which is strictly endocellular without any infectivity via purified particles: this is true for the vast majority of RNA viruses with only one documented exception supported by some in vitro mycocidal potential (Urayama et al., 2010; Urayama et al., 2016). Given this exception, the possibility environmental infectivity from purified particles seems to be instead a common feature of mycovirus-infecting members of the family *Genomoviridae* (Khalifa and MacDiarmid, 2021; Li et al., 2020; Yu et al., 2013).

4.2.1 RISK ASSESSMENT FOR HUMAN HEALTH OF MYCOVIRUS-INFECTING GENOMOVIRIDAE

Since the discovery of the first DNA virus infecting fungi in 2010 (Yu et al., 2010), shown to be related to the ssDNA plant infecting viruses of the family *Geminiviridae*, a great number of virus sequences were shown to be related to this initial *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum* ssDNA virus; such virus sequences were shown to have common features and a number of different genera and species can be accommodated in a rather conserved *Genomoviridae* family (Krupovic et al., 2016; Varsani and Krupovic, 2017, 2021).

So far there are 236 recognized species organized in 10 genera inside the family (Varsani and Krupovic, 2021). Interestingly from the Risk-assessment point of view, some of the viruses in this family are thought to infect many different vertebrate species including humans.

Although the first characterized member of the *Genomoviridae* was a fungal-infecting virus, among the hundreds of genomovirus isolates identified (545 genomovirids sequences) only 4 genomovirids are actually identified from fungi: three in the *Gemycircularvirus* genus (that comprises 251 genomovirids) and one from the newly established genus *Gemytripvirus* (Varsani and Krupovic, 2021). This recent review does not include a new virus species (at least 4 different isolates from different groups in different geographical areas, including one from VIROPLANT surveys) that should be accommodated in a new genus, or possibly in a new family (Hao et al., 2021; Khalifa and MacDiarmid, 2021; Ruiz-Padilla et al., 2021).

The rest of the genomovirids were identified in-silico, with only a minority actually isolated and characterized biologically; a great number were identified from environmental samples, but even those that were assigned to a specific host, can not be assumed to infect that host because fungi are ubiquitous in infecting higher organisms. Nevertheless, it is important to point out that a number of members of the genus *Gemykibivirus* are thought to infect humans although direct evidence of infected human cells was not provided yet: the association also with disease seem to be uncertain (Bezerra et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2019).

Even more relevant for our risk-assessment purposes are the cases of *Gemycircularvirus* (the same genus of the *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum* ssDNA virus hypothesized to be used as plant protection product) that were found in immunocompromised patients (Macera et al., 2019; Uch et al., 2015) or other human samples (Lamberto et al., 2014; Tung Gia et al., 2015).

Given that infectious clones of ssDNA mycovirus are available, their replication in human cells should be tested, in order to evaluate potential for infection.

To our knowledge none of these viruses were found incorporated in host genomes, therefore making less likely their integration in the genomes (therefore likely safe from the point of view of mutational possibility).

4.2.2 ENVIRONMENTAL RISK ASSESSMENT OF MYCOVIRUS-INFECTING GENOMOVIRIDAE

Given that members of the family *Genomoviridae* have been isolated from very diverse sample matrices it is very important to predict the likeliness of off-target effects when applied directly in the environment as plant protection products.

In the only extensively biologically characterized mycovirus, the possibility that the mycovirus could infect other fungal species from environmental contamination was investigated: SsHADV-1 could only infect two other *Sclerotinia* species, but not *B. cinerea*, *Magnaporthe oryzae* and *Coniothyrium minitans* through PEG transfection of protoplasts, showing that this virus has a rather specific host range in fungi (Yu et al., 2013).

The same DNA mycovirus was also tested for its capacity to replicate in plant cells, through attempts at in planta infection, and in cell hybridization: both assays confirmed persistence of particles and DNA but lack of replication (Yu et al., 2013).

Although these initial experiments seem to exclude the possibility that gemycirculaviruses infect plants, a number of other gemycirculavirus and genomovirus-like sequences are often found associated to plants (Chabi-Jesus et al., 2020; Fontenele et al., 2020; Lamas et al., 2016).

Another very interesting feature that was later discovered about SsHADV-1 is the fact that it is transmitted by a dipteran mycophagous insect (Liu et al., 2016): the virus can be acquired by the insect *Lycoriella ingenua* when feeding on infected mycelia; the authors showed indeed that the virus replicates in insect cells, extending therefore the host range to a non-fungal kingdom. This was also confirmed through in vitro infection of *Spodoptera frugiperda* cell lines (Liu et al., 2016). Other authors found the same virus from samples of dragonfly species (order Odonata) (Dayaram et al., 2015). Overall, while this virus seem to be rather confined to a few fungal species, it seems to be widely capable of infecting insects from different orders, increasing the risk of its use in the environment for possibly targeting other beneficial insect species, such as pollinators and parasitoid and predators. This raises the interesting possibility that this is indeed an insect virus that only recently adapted to infect fungi.

Regarding the possibility that this recently described class of mycoviruses could also infect other invertebrate and vertebrate animals, the fact that they are widespread in many birds and other environmental species should warrant their study in model system animals in order to properly assess the risk of their widespread use in agriculture as PPP.

4.3 A FURTHER EVOLUTION OF THE MYCOVIRUS-BASED BIOCONTROL APPROACH: THE FUNGAL ENDOPHYTIC APPROACH

As mentioned above three different works look at a new approach for the use of mycoviruses to protect annual crops: they all showed that presence of a mycovirus can turn a pathogenic fungus into an endophytic one, and the presence of the formerly pathogenic fungus as endophyte, protects the plant not only against the same virus-free pathogenic fungus, but also against other fungal pathogens: moreover the same virus-infected endophyte can also work on a non-host plant such as wheat to protect from infection from a number of different wheat pathogens, particularly fusarium head blight (Tian et al., 2020). In this case it is relevant for risk assessment that the dispersal in the environment is minimal since only the seeds are pre-treated, therefore limiting the environmental spread through drifts when the formulation is aimed at the canopy.

The common aspect of this approach is that the biologically active ingredient in a possible formulation is no longer the mycovirus (particles) but we go back to envision a treatment with the mycovirus-infected fungus. The novelty is that the biocontrol approach does not rely on transmission of the mycovirus to a recipient fungus, but the mechanism is likely plant-mediated; this aspect was well addressed in the case of *Pestalopsis theae* infected by a chrysovirus (Zhou et al., 2021). Such plant-mediated protection also worked in a mycovirus-caused hypervirulent *Leptosphaeria biglobosa* treated plant (the mycovirus being a dsRNA virus in the genus *Quadrivirus*), against *Leptosphaeria maculans*, bringing to an overall decrease of the severity of Phoma stem canker (Shah et al., 2020).

4.3.1: RISK ASSESSMENT FOR HUMANS (ENDOPHYTIC APPROACH)

In this case the risk assessment for humans should be carried out on the fungus, and likely the virus, contained inside the fungus without an extracellular phase, should be considered just a maternal genetic element; this view could be particularly true in the case of RNA mycoviruses (as are the cases of the Chrysovirus and Quadrivirus described above), while some possibility of an extracellular phase for the ssDNA virus in nature should be tested. If that's the case, the risk assessment for such a product for humans should focus on the fungal component, with well-established protocols already being in place that need to look in specific at the potential for causing infectious diseases in immuno-compromised patients or allergic reaction among other features.

4.3.2: RISK ASSESSMENT FOR THE ENVIRONMENT (ENDOPHYTIC APPROACH)

Before commercial use of new biocontrol agents, their safety needs to be assessed, taking into account their dispersal and persistence in the environment. Known mycoviruses with RNA genomes are strictly intracellular and would need to be applied to the field inside the mycelia or spores of their host fungus. This also means introducing new inocula of the host pathogen into the environment. For this reason, only environments already heavily infected with the pathogen can be considered for virocontrol treatments, and the introduced strain of the pathogen should be clearly hypovirulent. Moreover, unless the introduced host strain has the same genotype as the resident population, the genetic diversity of the host could be increased, which could potentially lead to the generation of new, more virulent host genotypes; this aspect can be addressed transfecting the mycovirus to cause endophytic behavior to a local strain.

In general, mycoviruses are expected to persist in the environment for a long time after application due to their persistent intracellular nature, depending also on the specificity of the fungal host-host plant interaction. A first element of Environmental Risk assessment for the endophytic approach (also termed schizotrophism in heterologous plant-host systems) is the fact that compared to the mycocidal approach, the bioavailability of the mycovirus in the environment is limited by its being inside the fungal cell.

The authors that termed schizotrophism the host-dependent trophism of some pathogenic/endophytic fungi also pointed out at the fact that in this case they are releasing in-field a non-pathogen (*S. sclerotiorum* on wheat), contrary to the previous approach of *S. sclerotiorum* strain DT-8 in *Brassica* field (Tian et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2020). In this specific case, long living sclerotia associated normally to the pathogen could contaminate the soil for longer times constituting inoculum source for the following years and following crops.

Another risk to be assessed is the potential virus transmission to non-target organisms. In general, mycoviruses are highly species-specific and no major interspecies spread is expected. However, mycoviruses have been shown to be occasionally transmitted between different species of the same fungal genus (Liu et al., 2003; Melzer et al., 2002; Schoebel et al., 2018; Vainio et al., 2011), or possibly even more distantly related fungal species in the same environment (Arjona-Lopez et al., 2018; Feldman et al., 2012; Vainio et al., 2017; Yaegashi and Kanematsu, 2016; Yaegashi et al., 2013). This is not expected to lead to problems if a common virus pool is naturally shared between multiple host species, in which case each species would be equally adapted to the virus effects. However, the outcome will be more unpredictable if non-native viruses are to be used. Due to the lack of co-evolution and adaptation, viral host jumps are expected to be harmful to the host fungus, as has been demonstrated in laboratory experiments (Chen et al., 1996; Jurvansuu et al., 2014; Kanematsu et al., 2010). If the introduced viruses would affect co-occurring ecologically important fungal species (including for example mutualistic endophytes or mycorrhizal species), their effects might reach beyond the fungal community and affect the functionality of the plant community and thereby the whole ecosystem.

An even more problematic scenario would be posed by virus transmission into other organisms that are closely connected with fungi, such as plants and arthropods. Recent high-throughput sequencing studies have suggested the occasional occurrence of such transmissions, at least on an evolutionary time scale (Shi et al., 2016); furthermore experimental cross kingdom experiments have shown the possibility for mycoviruses to infect plant cells, or plants altogether (Bian et al., 2020; Nerva et al., 2017).

The possibility of off-target effects of mycoviruses on insects is greatly diminished by the application of fungi, but as in the case of *L. ingenua*, such acquisition is possible, although no specific harm to the insect host was shown in that experiment: it remains to be established if the mycovirus can be acquired by the insect when carried by endophytic fungi: the mycophagous insect might not have access to the fungus in that case.

5. CASE STUDY 4: COMPREHENSIVE RISK ASSESSMENT OF A VIGS APPROACH AGAINST INSECTS AND FUNGAL TARGETS

5.1 VIGS AS AN ALTERNATIVE TO DSRNA FOR STIMULATION OF RNAI

5.1.1 OVERVIEW OF RNA INTERFERENCE (RNAi)

RNA interference (RNAi) is a natural phenomenon that silences gene expression at the post-transcriptional level (Catalanotto et al., 2000; Fire et al., 1998). It is a phenomenon present in most eukaryotic organisms, based on a pathway which has a set of conserved elements. Its original significance was as an anti-viral and anti-transposon pathway, but during evolution it has acquired also physiological significance in endogenous regulation of gene expression giving rise to a number of pathways such as the miRNA and piwiRNA pathways.

RNAi is homology dependent and stimulated by various forms of “aberrant” RNA. Such aberrant RNAs (often dsRNA of virus replication intermediate) are recognized by DICERs, a specific group of RNAses which cut the dsRNA in small RNAs (siRNAs) of specific sizes (mostly 21-25 nt) and initiate the silencing response. Such small RNAs are loaded in the RISC complex (a key component being Argonaute proteins -AGO) which finds mRNA with homology to the siRNAs and finally cuts the mRNA preventing its expression (in vertebrate, often inhibition of expression is through inhibition of translation). Figure 5.1.1-a displays the main molecular steps of RNAi.

Figure 5.1.1-a: Molecular pathway involved in post transcriptional gene silencing, stimulated by dsRNA or viral RNA.

In Plants and other higher organisms, the signal from siRNA can be amplified by a third set of genes involved in the pathway, host encoded RNA-dependent RNA polymerases (RdRP).

The discovery of this pathway brought immediately to possible translational applications, and ultimately to the possibility of new therapeutics. In facts, it was soon envisioned that specific dsRNA sequences targeting essential host genes could bring specific eukaryotic pest or pathogens to death or strongly diminish their overall fitness.

An important aspect to consider is the extent to which RNAi stimulus acts in the body of the target organism: in this respect the stimulus can act in a i) cell autonomous way (i.e. dsRNA initiate RNAi only in the

cells where it is present) ii) non cell autonomous/systemic (i.e. a signal, including dsRNA itself, can move and expand the RNAi to distant cells and tissues that did not receive a direct stimulus from dsRNA and iii) environmental, which relates to the capacity of the organism to uptake dsRNA directly from the environment. In this respect we must point out that different metazoans have very different responses to stimulus: the initial *C. elegans* work pointed to a very easy environmental uptake and systemic response of dsRNA and two mechanisms were elucidated, a specific channel mediated one (SID-1 and SID-2 genes) (Winston et al., 2002; Winston et al., 2007) and an endocytosis-dependent mechanism (Huvenne and Smaghe, 2010; Jose et al., 2009). In other organisms, even very closely related ones, such mechanisms are not in place, and this has relevant consequences both for efficacy of treatment and risk assessment (Kolliopoulou et al., 2017).

The signal can be amplified through an RdRP-dependent mechanism, in plants (Vazquez and Hohn, 2013), nematodes, and fungi . Such amplification mechanisms is absent in insects and vertebrates.

5.1.2 CLASSES OF DSRNA-BASED PRODUCTS

As mentioned above, the potential targets in pests and pathogens (excluding prokaryotes) are all those genes whose downregulation affects host fitness (to different degrees). The main difference between dsRNA-based products and conventional chemical pesticides is that the former act specifically at the expression level, while the latter interfere at downstream events, mostly interacting with the proteome.

An RNAi product was indeed registered for the first time by the USA EPA in 2017 against western corn rootworms (WCR, *Diabrotica virginifera*) (Shaffer, 2020). Although such approach was thought to overcome the problem of resistance, it was shown that indeed a laboratory population of WCR developed resistance to dsRNA in general through inactivation of the general gut uptake mechanism (Khajuria et al., 2018).

In general, the EPA has envisioned four types of dsRNA-based products, but further development could be expected

- i) Direct control agents: they specific target pest-pathogen genes, whose downregulation impacts the host-fitness
- ii) Suppressors of resistance factors: this is linked to the possibility that resistance to some pesticides is linked to “resistance factors”. Including downregulation of such factors can re-establish sensitivity of the host to the pesticide
- iii) Affect Growth regulators: instead of acting specifically with the hormone action, dsRNA could affect the synthesis of specific enzymes involved in hormone biosynthesis
- iv) Affect Plant Growth regulators.

5.1.3 VIRUS INDUCED GENE SILENCING (VIGS) FOR PEST/PATHOGEN CONTROL THROUGH RNAI APPROACH

Given the promising aspects of the translational applications of RNAi to contrast pests and pathogens, it is somewhat surprising that so-far only the RNAi stimulated through a dsRNA from a transgene has overcome the regulatory hurdle and gained access to market.

One of the main bottlenecks to the use of free dsRNA is related to their stability and efficient delivery to target host (being them insects, fungi, plants etc.). There have been a number of different approaches to increment stability and delivery efficiency that can be organized in two main categories: i) use of nanoparticles and ii) use of transformed microorganisms to deliver dsRNA.

Among the different nanomaterials used to stabilize and increase the availability of dsRNA, a number of studies showed the efficacy of chitosan, liposomes, nanoclay (Das et al., 2015; Whyard et al., 2009; Zhang et al., 2010).

DsRNA delivery by transformed microorganisms started with the use of RNase III-deficient *E. coli* strain HT115(DE3) (Kamath and Ahringer, 2003; Tian et al., 2009). Other alternatives relate to transformed algae and yeast (Fei et al., 2021; Murphy et al., 2016).

A possible alternative is the use of engineered viruses: such approach called Virus induced gene silencing (VIGS) has been mostly used in model system host plants and insects for reverse genetic high throughput screens. But it also can be considered a possible way to deliver stimulators of RNAi: in facts most RNA viruses accumulate fairly abundant dsRNA during their replication, and DNA virus can also be considered to express hairpin RNA that induce specific RNAi (Gu et al., 2011; Huang et al., 2007). The main advantage of using virus vectors for VIGS is their specificity, since they can be chosen according to their very specific host range (which is not the case of transformed bacteria). Furthermore, viruses themselves can carry the stimulators systemically if that is their normal fate.

In VIROPLANT we envision for the first time a VIGS approach against fungi using a mycovirus vector based on *Cryphonectria hypovirus 1* (CHV-1) (Figure 5.1.3-a). We have engineered the insertion of 100-300 bp fragments at the end of ORF-A a site that was shown to accommodate in-frame fragments without affecting replication (Suzuki et al., 2000). To our knowledge this would be the first VIGS vector derived from mycoviruses.

The target genes are from *B. cinerea*:

- [BcmEF2](<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/5436745>): elongation factor

- [BcCYP51](<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/5430454>): CYP51-like; cytochrome P450 family 51 and similar cytochrome P450s

- [Bcchs1](<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/5435893>): CHS_like; Chalcone and stilbene synthases; plant-specific polyketide synthases (PKS) and related enzymes, also called type III PKSs

CHV1 12,734 nts

CHV1 VIGS for a Botrytis gene: Eburicol 14a –demethylase (CYP51)

Figure 5.1.3-a: Genome organization of CHV1 and a VIGS vector expressing a fragment targeting *Botrytis cinerea*

Insect VIGS vectors are also at the very initial stage of development: the first one used to initiate an RNAi response is based on the infectious clone of Flock House virus, a bipartite RNA virus in the *Nodaviridae* (Figure 5.1.3-b) (Taning et al., 2018)

Figure 5.1.3-b: Genome organization of a Nodavirus

Another insect-specific virus that was developed in a VIGS vector is based on Cricket paralysis virus (CPV) (Figure 5.1.3-c) (Matsumura et al., 2020).

Figure 5.1.3-c: Cricket paralysis Virus Genome organization (from Viral Zone)

In VIROPLANT we target insects with two distinct VIGS approaches: in one case we use an established plant virus, tobacco rattle virus (TRV)-based VIGS vector (Figure 5.1.3-d) widely used in VIGS plant reverse genetic approaches (Ratcliff et al., 2001). Following former experimental approaches that used plant viruses to stimulate RNAi for metazoans (Dubreuil et al., 2009) and insects (Hajeri et al., 2014; Kumar et al., 2012; Wuriyangan and Falk, 2013) we also envisioned cloning in the multiple cloning site of TRV the following gene fragments:

For *Frankliniella occidentalis*:

-V-type proton ATPase subunit B (XM_026437356.1)

-toll-like receptor 6 (XM_026419137.1)

For *Thrips tabaci*:

-V-type proton ATPase subunit B (GFQQ01015656.1 TSA: *Thrips tabaci* isolate Punjab-Faridkot transcript_15697, transcribed RNA sequence)

-SNF7 (GFQQ01012287.1 TSA: *Thrips tabaci* isolate Punjab-Faridkot transcript_12322, transcribed RNA sequence; blast con multivesicular body protein 7 in *Frankliniella*)

Figure 5.1.3-d: Genome organization of tobacco rattle virus and a derived expression vector.

Another VIGS vector we are considering in VIROPLANT requires the development of a new infectious clone from an insect-specific virus that we found abundantly accumulating in a population of *T. tabaci* from the Italian Riviera (Chiapello et al., 2021) (Figure 5.1.3-e). This bipartite sobemo-like virus (MN725051 and MN725052) is likely to be a successful VIGS vector since it is phylogenetically related to plant sobemoviruses which can be successfully developed in expression vectors.

Figure 5.1.3-e: Genome organization of *Thrips tabaci* sobemo-like virus and the VIGS vector derived from it.

5.2 SUMMARY OF THEORETICAL RISKS FOR DOUBLE STRANDED RNA PRODUCTS

A recent OECD conference has resulted in a thorough document addressing the environmental risk assessment of dsRNA-based pesticide: the full document is available to the general public at the following link: [https://www.oecd.org/officialdocuments/publicdisplaydocumentpdf/?cote=env/jm/mono\(2020\)26&doclanguage=en](https://www.oecd.org/officialdocuments/publicdisplaydocumentpdf/?cote=env/jm/mono(2020)26&doclanguage=en)

Parts of the conference proceedings have also been published in peer review journals, and an array of papers have looked at the regulatory framework of the registration of dsRNA-based PPP and other issues related to dsRNA PPP risk assessment in the last two years (Dietz-Pfeilstetter et al., 2021; Fletcher et al., 2020; Romeis and Widmer, 2020; Wytinck et al., 2020). Here below we will summarize the main issues, particularly focusing on off-targets effect, on vertebrates and other eukaryotic organisms.

5.2.1: MODELS OF OFF-TARGET EFFECTS

A well designed dsRNA to be used as PPP can i) have the required detrimental effect only on the target gene in the target organism; ii) have also off target effects on other genes in the target organism only; iii) have off-target effects on different species from the target species on the homologous gene; iv) have off target effects both on off-target organisms and off target genes; the latter two models imply the possibility of hazards that need to be properly addressed in risk assessment.

Three main prerequisites/aspects need to be considered when considering off-target effect:

- i) Potential for exposure of off-target organisms

- ii) Responsiveness to dsRNA of non-target organisms: this has to be considered on a case by case, since dsRNA is differently effective in different organisms (no effects for example in *S. cerevisiae* since the RNAi machinery is absent).
- iii) Sequence alignment: this is a basic requirement (stringency is different in different organisms) for a biologically meaningful interaction.

5.2.2: EFFECTS ON HUMANS: MODELLED FROM HUMAN RNAI-BASED THERAPEUTICS

Given the great potential of using RNAi to address a number of Human diseases (Bumcrot et al., 2006), a wealth of literature exists on the pharmacokinetics of dsRNA derived molecules: therefore it is important to extrapolate from those studies the real possibility that an RNAi-based PPP can exert its off-target effects on humans.

In general, a dsRNA therapeutic can have three categories of off target effects on human/vertebrate:

- i) miRNA-like off target, referring to the sequence-dependent unintended mRNA regulation
- ii) inflammatory response through the activation of Toll-like receptors triggered aspecifically by dsRNA/siRNA (Cho et al., 2009)
- iii) saturation of the RNAi machinery of the host because of high dosage (it generally happens only in experimental conditions with human cell cultures).

It is to be noticed that RNA in itself is not allergenic, but co-formulants and contamination from purification process could still be an issue.

Given this premises it must be noticed that indeed one of the main constraints to the use of RNAi therapeutics in humans is their limited oral bioavailability and the rapid rate of clearance from circulation: delivery to the proper intracellular site remains a major challenge (Juliano, 2016).

In this respect all the off-target effects concerns in humans are raised by intravenous studies (to facilitate reaching the target tissue/cell): but dsRNA used as PPP would actually be exposed to humans through ingestion (diet). Such route minimizes the real exposure to human cells, since a number of barriers are in place that inactivate the dsRNA before crossing gut barrier.

As for the sequence of the dsRNA, a number of studies has looked at the possibility of off-target sites from all the different sRNA originating from a certain dsRNA. Such in silico analysis have shown indeed the potential for off target both in target organisms and in off-target organisms. For vertebrates (humans) a further effect is that the exact match of 7 nt in position 2 to 8 of the guide strand of a small RNA can indeed inhibit translation if the match is the 3' untranslated region of a messenger RNA. One example of such in-silico prediction studies showed that the probability of off-target ranged from 5 to 80% in *Schizosaccharomyces pombe*, *Caenorhabditis elegans* and *Homo sapiens* transcriptomes, when considering all the possible siRNA sequences from 17 to 28 nt long derived from a dsRNA of 100-400 nt (Qiu et al., 2005) . Similar conclusions were drawn based on an in-silico study carried out in *D. melanogaster* (Kulkarni et al., 2006).

5.2.3: OFF TARGET EFFECTS IN DIFFERENT ORGANISMS

A basic aspect that needs to be considered in off-target effect is how different species respond to exogenous RNAs. In general, different organisms vary significantly in their ability to take up foreign dsRNA and use it to jump start their RNAi pathway. RNAi pathway is generally conserved among eukaryotes, but some components differ significantly: this is particularly true for different mechanisms of cellular uptake and systemic spread of silencing (Joga et al., 2016).

5.2.3A RNAI IN DIFFERENT ORGANISMS

i) Microorganisms

In the case of prokaryotes, RNA was known to have regulatory function well-before the description of eukaryotic miRNA and siRNA, nevertheless the mechanism is completely different acting on non-orthologous set of proteins. In specific to act in the CRISPR-CAS pathway, RNA needs to have a specific conserved secondary structure that is not present in siRNA acting in RNAi (Marraffini, 2015)

In fungi and protozoa, the RNAi pathway is mostly conserved but with some specificities and total loss in some organisms (i.e. *S. cerevisiae* *Trypanosoma cruzi*, *Leishmania major*) (DaRocha et al., 2004; Quoc and Nakayashiki, 2015; Robinson and Beverley, 2003)

ii) Non arthropod invertebrates

In this case, much concentration has been paid to *C. elegans*, the model species of the phylum Nematoda. In this case environmental RNAi can be up-taken both by soaking and feeding. In other worm species, such uptake is not as efficient (Félix, 2008). Another aspect that was studied in detail in *C. elegans* is the systemic spread of the silencing signal and the amplification of the signal by RdRP: both occur in the model species, but a wide difference in response is species-specific and cannot be assumed for the whole phylum (Wheeler et al., 2012).

iii) Arthropods

Arthropods comprise two main classes of organisms that are relevant to plant protection: Insects and Arachnids. Given that most pests for a possible target of RNAi-based PPP are insects, it becomes very important to know the degree of conservation and variation in response to RNAi stimulators in different orders represented in these two groups of arthropods. A number of considerations are summarized in a recent literature review from EFSA (Christiaens et al., 2018). Insect are the most common targets for RNAi, and it is important to know that their response can vary a lot among orders, being some coleopteran species the most responsive ones, and the model species *Drosophila melanogaster* one of the least responsive.

Briefly two mechanisms are responsible for uptake of dsRNA in insects: one relies on a specific transmembrane channel, likely in analogy to SID-1 of *C. elegans*, even if they are not proper orthologues, and therefore the Sid1-

like terminology should be used (Tomoyasu et al., 2008). The second mechanism seems to be common to all insect orders and relies on endocytosis through clathrin coated vesicles (Saleh et al., 2006).

The second gene that was shown to play an important role in *C. elegans* (SID-2) does not have an orthologue in insects.

The other main feature is also the possible absence of signal amplification through RdRP in insects, with some incongruencies in the literature (Li et al., 2018).

A number of reviews has looked at the different responsiveness among different orders and summarized them in tables: here we only point out at the fact that while dipterans and lepidopterans are among the least responsive, hemipterans (often virus and phytoplasma vectors) are quite responsive, arriving to the most responsive ones which are coleopterans. Also a different stadial responsiveness was also shown with early instar more responsive than others in *Leptinotarsa decemlineata* (Guo et al., 2015).

In arachnids, most of the studies on RNAi have concentrated on mites since a number of them are considered important plant pests, and *Varroa* spp. is an important mite affecting honeybees. The general consensus of a very limited number of studies on spider mites and varroa is that they are sensitive to RNAi and that they can be affected by environmental RNAi. Furthermore it seems that RdRP are often present in mites (Van Leeuwen et al., 2013).

v) Plants

Plants are among the first organisms where the RNAi pathway was thoroughly investigated. Here below we summarize some of the main features RNAi has in plants: **i)** the cuticle is a barrier to environmental silencing, and most experiments required some “help” to pass this barrier; **ii)** in plants, the effect of RNAi can be systemic, with amplification of the signal; **iii)** in plants, miRNAs are usually perfectly or nearly perfectly complementary to their target gene, and induce cleavage of the mRNA with the RISC complex (while in animals the target can be just the seed of 8nt, and often translation is inhibited) (Jones-Rhoades et al., 2006); **iv)** plant miRNAs display a 2'-O-methyl group as protectant (Yu et al., 2005); **v)** plants possess transitive RNA, which are new siRNAs that originate after cleavage from a specific mRNA (secondary siRNA that have a distinct target from the original miRNA) (Manavella et al., 2012); **vi)** extracellular transport of sRNAs could be similar to mammals, as exosome or microvesicles (Colombo et al., 2014; Fritz et al., 2016).

vi) Fish, Reptiles Birds

The information about RNAi in non-mammal vertebrates is scant but RNAi has only been achieved in cell lines or embryos, therefore the general barrier to alimentary uptake of dsRNA are likely to be acting in all vertebrates (Sifuentes-Romero et al., 2011).

vii) Mammals

A paper from 2012 raised the possibility that the ingested miRNA from plant could act on animal metabolism (Zhang and Ruvkun, 2012). This raised a lot of interest, but the results were finally considered an artifact. In another case that supported the same contention the paper was retracted (Pastrello et al., 2017). Animal models (primates and mice) also confirmed absence of a biological effect from dietary plant miRNA (Dickinson et al., 2013; Witwer and Hirschi, 2014). Also an analysis of 800 datasets from siRNA from different human tissues and bodily fluids excluded that plant miRNA could have a biological role (Kang et al., 2017). The same conclusion was confirmed by a meta-analysis (Chan and Snow, 2017). This is now the general consensus of US-EPA, there is no reliable evidence that dsRNA taken up from the gut into mammalian circulation can have any biological effect.

5.2.3B UNINTENDED RNAI EFFECTS IN DIFFERENT ORGANISMS

There are two main approaches to try to assess the risk for non-target organisms (NTO) of a putative dsRNA product: one is to try to predict *in silico* the effect on NTO, taking in consideration their genomic/transcriptomic sequences (when known) and the specific properties of their RNAi machinery; the second approach is instead experimental, looking at the biological effect of doses of a specific dsRNA product (Bachman et al., 2013; Bolognesi et al., 2012; Roberts et al., 2015; Whyard et al., 2009). The *in-silico* approach is currently not considered safe and its use is limited.

- i) in humans/mammals: as mentioned above since the registration of a miRNA based drug by the FDA and EMA named Onpattro™ a thorough study of the kinetic of dsRNA based products in humans has been carried out and is helpful in assessing the risk and hazards of dsRNA derived products used as PPP. The general consensus is that the combination of RNAses and acids found in the human digestive system are likely to ensure that all forms of RNA structure are degraded throughout the digestive process. Furthermore, a number of physical and biochemical barriers are in place before reaching the final target cells: dsRNA needs to pass gastro-intestinal (GI) cell membranes, then cell to endothelium, across endothelium to blood and tissues across tissue membranes.

Also a number of dose-toxicity studies in mammalian test species did not indicate direct toxicity of large doses of dsRNA (Petrick et al., 2016). The same can be said for the immune system stimulation: the theoretical potential of dsRNA being able to stimulate innate immune response in animal creating inflammation is mitigated by the fact that in order to obtain in model organisms some inflammation the route of exposure needs to be intravenous injection. A third aspect often considered is the risk of saturating the RNAi machinery, but even in this case, although some effects in this regards were likely occurring in cell cultures (Khan et al., 2009) or in mice with specific on site hi-dose viral vector derived artificial delivery (Grimm et al., 2006). Nevertheless, again, there is no evidence that the massive RNAs in its various forms present in plants and animals normally ingested by humans stimulate any saturation, likely because mechanism to prevent such occurrence are in place, even if sequence complementarity with human genes is widespread (Jensen et al., 2013).

- ii) In birds, reptiles fish earthworms: in this case, most studies related to hazard were only carried out with cell lines and embryos. Only recently a wide study to register DvSnf dsRNA against WCR by USEPA reported no effects on broiler chickens, bobwhite quail, channel catfish, and annelid earthworms (USEPA 2016 <https://www.regulations.gov/document?D=EPA-HQ-OPP-2016-0349-0009>)
- iii) Honeybee: the same study to register the same dsRNA based product also looked at high exposure doses by feeding continuously for 14 days and no effects were seen on life cycle parameters both for larvae and adults.
- iv) Other arthropods: the same study also looked at a number of ecologically important (predators and secondary parasites) insects from various orders, but not effects on survival, development or growth and reproductive properties of any of the beetles, wasps, green lacewing etc tested.

5.3: FATE OF DS-RNA IN THE ENVIRONMENT AND PLANTS

Although this aspect is important to measure the persistence of dsRNA in the environment and the potential for exposure, the properties of dsRNA are very different from our true target of risk-assessment which is RNAi through VIGS: viruses are generally protected by a protein coat which changes completely their properties in the environment. Therefore we will only briefly summarize the main points related to dsRNA monitoring and fate in the environment described previously (Bachman et al., 2020).

A specific underlying problem is the standardization of the detection methodology to monitor dsRNA in the environment: this is important when different formulations will be compared in different studies; initial results with QuantiGene technology seem to be encouraging (Armstrong et al., 2013), but other approaches are also under consideration (radiolabeled dsRNA) (Parker et al., 2019).

The general consensus of a number of studies on dsRNA ectopically sprayed in the environment is the very little persistence and labile nature of dsRNA in soil, water and sediments: their inactivation/degradation is mostly operated by microbes (Albright et al., 2017; Fischer et al., 2017). This instability in the environment has been a bottleneck for the efficacy of ectopic treatment and proper formulation are necessary to increase the potential for success in the field: therefore, if indeed dsRNA in itself is not really a major concern for lasting pollution in the environment, the specific formulations should be considered on a case by case since the degradation kinetics could differ substantially.

A further specific aspect is the possibility of uptake and amplification in plants of ectopically sprayed dsRNA: a number of studies showed that such occurrence is possible, but only in detached leaf assay, abrasion, wounding or stabilizing formulations (Koch et al., 2016; Konakalla et al., 2016; Mitter et al., 2017; Song et al., 2018): this limits the possible off-target effect of siRNA on plants.

Also secondary amplification is possible in plants through a number of different mechanisms, but they require a high expression of the stimulating signal (aberrant RNA or viral, or others) (Dubrovina and Kiselev, 2019; Frizzi

and Huang, 2010). Nevertheless, given that such amplification does not result in increased exposure to off target (particularly vertebrates) such aspect becomes less relevant.

5.4 THE “EXTRA”THEORETICAL RISKS OF A VIGS APPROACH FOR RNAI

The controversy about the origin of SarsCov-2 virus has raised the attention of the public to the study and use of recombinant viruses, and even if there is a large consensus among scientists that the most parsimonious origin of the Sars-Cov2 genome is natural, through an intermediate vertebrate host (Andersen et al., 2020; Seyran et al., 2021; Temmam et al., 2021), the possibility of using recombinant viruses released in the environment is likely ended for generations, due to a general mistrust and sensitivity in the general public.

Nevertheless it is important here to point out that host jumps are limited to relatively closely related hosts: for example, there are no plant viruses that can infect vertebrates (a barrier likely similar to that among phages and vertebrates), even though some poor and/or overinterpreted studies pollute the literature raising confusion in non-experts (Baliq et al., 2015; Bousbia et al., 2010; Colson et al., 2010; Jiwaji et al., 2019; Jiwaji et al., 2016; Kim et al., 2020; Knowland, 1974; Koudelka et al., 2009).

Therefore, it seems that VIGS vector derived from plant viruses should not pose any threat to humans. The same can be said for other animal (vertebrate and invertebrate) off target effects, excluding those that belong to clades able to actively infect both plants and insects (but because they are negative stranded RNA viruses they are not good candidates for VIGS vectors).

The same can be said for VIGS vectors derived from mycoviruses: no evidence of infectivity, pathogenicity or toxicity can occur to vertebrates from mycovirus vector.

A further element that needs to be pointed out is that recombinant virus can be generally made less harmful (for example TMV without the CP) and less likely to spread naturally in the environment once disarmed.

Finally, much is said about the potential for further recombination of recombinant VIGS vectors: such occurrence is likely, but it generally results in the loss of the insert, which leaves the virus with lower fitness compared to the wild type virus.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This brief overview of the “theoretical” risk assessment is meant to be an initial inventory of predictable hazards posed by the use of virus-based biocontrol agents in agriculture: it must be observed that some viruses have been used for years in agriculture (baculoviruses) without leaving any specific detectable trace of their use in human health or for their environmental impact. Nevertheless, baculoviruses as a class of viruses have a very limited host range, that is not reflected in the host range of some of the viruses we envision, which have a strict host range per se, but belong to groups that can have a wider range of taxonomic hosts, to use as biocontrol agents in the future; properly assessing the risk with appropriate experimental approaches will be a task to be

implemented when a technically valid virus-based alternative will rise for important plant diseases with limited control options.

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